

Studies on Adsorption Indicators : Substituted Phthalide and Tetrachlorophthalides in Argentometric Titrations

E. SINGH and P. C. GUPTA*

Department of Chemistry, Ewing Christian College, Allahabad

Manuscript received 25 May 1973 ; revised 12 July 1974 ; accepted 18 July 1974

In the course of studies of some new phthalide and tetrachlorophthalides for their use as indicators in argentometric titrations it has been found that 3-(2', 4'-dihydroxyphenyl) 4,5-dimethoxyphthalide (I) is quite comparable to fluorescein, 3-methyl-3-(2', 4'-dihydroxyphenyl) 4,5,6,7-tetrachlorophthalide (II) shows good adsorbility for chloride ions and slighter than (I) for bromide, Iodide, and thiocyanate ions. 3-phenyl-3-(2', 4'-dihydroxyphenyl) 4,5,6,7-tetrachlorophthalide (III) shows poor adsorbility.

THE discovery of Fajans¹ in 1923, led to a good amount of work on the use of dyes as adsorption indicators ; the well-studied being fluorescein (resorcionolphthalein) in argentometric titration of halides, the theory of which is due originally to Fajans² and later modified by Kolthoff³. In the present communication the study has been extended to the unsymmetric phthalein dyes (I-III).

Results and Discussion

The adsorbility and colour changes of the dyes (I-III) have been compared with fluorescein as follows :

3-(2', 4'-dihydroxyphenyl) 4, 5-dimethoxyphthalide (I) : Adsorbility good ; titration possible for Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , and CNS^- . Suspension (Cl^- , white ; Br^- , yellowish-white ; I^- , yellow ; CNS^- , white to yellowish-white) \rightarrow pink ppt.

3-methyl-3-(2', 4'-dihydroxyphenyl) 4,5,6,7-tetrachlorophthalide (II) : Adsorbility good for chloride ions ; slighter than (I) for bromide, Iodide, and thiocyanate ions. Suspension (Cl^- , white ; Br^- , yellowish white ; I^- , yellowish-white ; CNS^- , white) \rightarrow pink ppt.

3-phenyl-3-(2', 4'-dihydroxyphenyl) 4, 5, 6, 7-tetrachlorophthalide (III) : Adsorbility poor ; Suspension as in (II). Cl^- , \rightarrow white ppt. ; Br^- \rightarrow yellow ppt. ; I^- , and CNS^- \rightarrow light pink ppt.

Fluorescein : Well-known for the titrations of halides and thiocyanate ions. Yellow suspension (Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , and CNS^-) \rightarrow pink ppt.

The absorption maxima of fluorescein and the above dyes (I-III) are almost the same but there is variation in adsorbility. The behaviour of these dyes can not be fully explained by Fajans² theory of secondary adsorption or by Kolthoff's³ theory of exchange adsorption. Since halogen substitution in the acid part of the dyes decreases adsorbility hence the results partly agree with the Fajans² views. But at the same time the adsorbility might also be depending on 3-substituted CH_3 - and C_6H_5 - group in II and III respectively.

Experimental

Material : AgNO_3 , NaCl , KCNS were B. D. H. analaR grade reagents and KI (M & B).

Indicator Solution : A 0.1% solution of the dye was prepared in rectified spirit, Eight drops of the indicator were used for every 10 ml of the solution titrated.

Preparation of the Dyes : The necessary acids o-Acetyltetrachlorobenzoic and o-Benzoyltetrachlorobenzoic acids were prepared by standard methods^{4,5} and then condensed with resorcinol by the method⁶. 3:4-Dimethoxy-o-phthalaldehydic acid was also condensed with resorcinol by the method⁷.

*Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad, India.

E. SINGH & P. C. GUPTA : STUDIES ON ABSORPTION INDICATORS

TABLE—DYE (I) USED AS ADSORPTION INDICATOR. VOLUME OF HALIDE AND THIOCYANATE TAKEN FOR TITRATION : 10 ml ; DROPS OF THE INDICATOR USED : 8 DROPS ; IN NEUTRAL MEDIUM.

Concentration of solution	Volume and Conc. of AgNO ₃ used	Transition of colour	Remarks
0.1N NaCl	10.00 ml 0.1N	white suspn. → pink ppt.	Coagulation starts shortly before the end point ; the ppt. attains light pink shade which changes to deep pink at the end point.
0.01N NaCl	10.02 ml 0.01N	white suspn. → pink ppt.	Coagulation takes place at the end point ; the end point is sharp.
0.1N KBr	10.00 ml 0.1N	yellowish-white suspn. → pink ppt.	Coagulation starts almost at the end point ; the end point is sharp.
0.01N KBr	9.99 ml 0.01N	yellowish-white suspn. → pink ppt.	Coagulation takes place at the end point ; the end point is sharp.
0.1N KI	10.00 ml 0.1N	yellow suspn. → pink ppt.	Coagulation starts 2 drops before the end point; sharp colour change (orange-pink) takes place at the end point.
0.01N KI	10.00 ml 0.01N	yellow suspn. → pink ppt.	Coagulation takes place at the end point ; the end point is sharp.
0.004N KI	10.02 ml 0.004N	yellow soln. → orange ppt.	Coagulation takes place at the end point ; titration is possible.
0.1N KCNS	10.00 ml 0.1N	white suspn. → pink ppt.	Coagulation starts before the end point but the sharp change in colour (light pink) and complete coagulation takes place at the end point.
0.02N KCNS	9.99 ml 0.02N	yellowish-white suspn. → pink ppt.	Coagulation takes place at the end point ; the point is sharp.
0.01N KCNS	10.00 ml 0.01N	yellowish-buff suspn. → pink ppt.	the suspension attains sharp pink colour at the end point and coagulates after much shaking and standing.

The following points emerge on comparing the above dye with fluorescein :

1. *Titration of Chloride Ions against Silver Ions* : The titration of chloride ions against silver ions can be best done with 0.1N and 0.05N solutions. With 0.01N solution the end point is also sharp and the titration is possible. Titrations can not be done with further dilution and are possible in neutral medium only. Fluorescein as an adsorption indicator can also be used up to 0.01N dilution.

2. *Titration of Bromide Ions against Silver Ions* : The end points are quite sharp till 0.01N dilutions. Fluorescein also does not give sharp end points beyond 0.01N dilution.

3. *Titration of Iodide Ions against Silver Ions* : The titrations can best be done with 0.1N and 0.05N solutions, and are possible till 0.004N dilutions. Fluorescein can not be used beyond 0.01N dilution.

4. *Titration of Thiocyanate Ions against Silver Ions* : Titrations can best be done with 0.1N and 0.05N solution ; with 0.01N solution coagulation is complete after much shaking and standing. Fluorescein can be used well up to 0.05N dilution but with 0.01N dilution the colour change at the end point is not

sharp ; the orange-yellow suspension changes to orange suspension and coagulates to pink ppt. after much shaking and standing.

References

1. K. FAJANS and O. HASSEL, *Z. Elektrochem. angew. physik. Chem.*, 1923, 29, 495 ; Cf. *Z. analyt. Chem.*, 1924, 64, 351.
2. K. FAJANS, *Die Chemische Analyse* Bd. 33, Neure β analyt. Methoden, 1935, S, 161.
3. I. M. KOLTHOFF and W. D. LARSON., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 56, 1881 ; Cf. *Z. Analyt. Chem.*, 1935, 103, 207.
4. E. SINGH and P. C. GUPTA., *Ann. Chim.*, 1972, 7, 291.
5. F. LEWENZ and K. T. SERIJAN., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 5753.
6. E. SINGH and P. C. GUPTA., *Ann. Chim.*, 1972, 7, 359.
7. E. SINGH and P. C. GUPTA., *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973 (in press).